

$\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COOH})$ (1) : $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.49 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in 0.05 M H_2SO_4 and mixed with a solution of TSA (3.06 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in $\text{NH}_3 - \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ (0.025 M). The resulting colourless solution was acidified with dilute H_2SO_4 upto the final concentration of 0.05 M. All operations were done in the absence of air. The precipitated colourless complex (1) was filtered and kept under reduced pressure (Found: Cu, 29.30; total S, 14.80; mercaptide S, 14.80. $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{SC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COOH})$ requires: Cu, 29.29; total S, mercaptide S, 14.75%).

$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{HSC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COOH})_2\text{SO}_4$ (2) : $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.49 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in 2 M H_2SO_4 was mixed with TSA (3.06 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in $\text{NH}_3 - \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ (0.025 M). A sparingly soluble precipitated deep blue complex (2) was filtered and kept under reduced pressure (Found: Cu, 13.58; total S, 20.50; mercaptide S, 13.70; sulphate S, 6.80. $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{HSC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COOH})_2\text{SO}_4$ requires: Cu, 13.57; total S, 20.47, mercaptide S, 13.65; sulphate S, 6.84%).

Results and Discussion

The colourless compound (1) readily transforms to an intensely blue product on exposure to air most presumably due to the oxidation of Cu^{I} to Cu^{II} . The blue compound (2) undergoes slow decomposition if kept in contact with the mother liquor. The $\nu_{\text{S-H}}$ band occurring at 2560 cm^{-1} for TSA was absent in the ir spectra of the complexes 1 and 2, suggesting SH coordination. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band at 1650 cm^{-1} remained unaltered, which indicates that carbonyl group was not involved in coordination.

In case of the Cu^{II} complex 2, the ir spectrum showed the presence of SO_4^{2-} bands at 1100 cm^{-1} . It is difficult to draw conclusions from the ir spectrum about the bonding arrangement around Cu^{II} . The intense blue colour of the complex, however, strongly suggests a charge transfer absorption characteristic of SH coordination since neither the SO_4^{2-} ion nor the COOH group alone or together can give such high absorptions. They are characteristic of Cu^{II} -thiolatocarboxylate complexes such as with thioglycolic acid, α -mercaptopropionic acid and thiomalic acid.

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Ternary Complexes of Nickel(II) with 2,2'-Bipyridyl or Histidine as Primary Ligand and Glycollic, Lactic, Malic and the corresponding Amino Acids as Secondary Ligands

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FORMATION constants of some hydroxy and the corresponding amino acid complexes of Ni^{II} having 2,2'-bipyridyl or histidine as the primary ligand have been determined in aqueous solution using modified form of Irving-Rossotti titration techniques¹. Amino acids form stronger chelates than the corresponding hydroxy acids.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Nickel perchlorate, sodium hydroxide and perchloric acid solutions were standardised by complexometric² and acid-base³ methods. For each system five sets of the solutions each of initial volume 50.00 ml having an ionic strength $I=0.2\text{ M}$ (NaClO_4) were pH-metrically titrated against standard NaOH

Fig. 1. pH titrations curves for the Ni^{II} -histidine-glycine system at 30° , $I=0.2\text{ M}$ (NaClO_4): (1) $0.02\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.002\text{ M histidine} + 0.178\text{ M NaClO}_4$, (2) $0.022\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.178\text{ M NaClO}_4$, (3) $0.02\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.002\text{ M histidine} + 0.002\text{ M Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 + 0.176\text{ M NaClO}_4$, (4) $0.022\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.002\text{ M glycine} + 0.176\text{ M NaClO}_4$ and (5) $0.02\text{ M HClO}_4 + 0.002\text{ M histidine} + 0.002\text{ M glycine} + 0.002\text{ M Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 + 0.174\text{ M NaClO}_4$; initial volume = 50 ml, $[\text{NaOH}] = 0.2\text{ M}$.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Ni^{II} COMPLEXES*Temp.=30°, Ionic strength=0.2 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand (HL)	pK_1^H	pK_2^H	pK_3^H	$\log K_{Ni.L}^{Ni}$	$\log K_{Ni.(bipy).L}^{Ni.(bipy)}$	$\log K_{Ni.(hist.).L}^{Ni.(hist.)}$
Glycollic acid	10.53	3.48	—	4.76	5.09	3.53
Lactic acid	10.90	3.53	—	5.01	5.12	4.07
Malic acid	11.90	4.64	3.05	5.50	5.22	4.57
Glycine	9.60	2.31	—	5.90	5.50	4.89
α -Alanine	9.76	2.31	—	5.54	5.14	4.64
Aspartic acid	9.60	3.60	—	7.12	6.72	4.78

*Limits of error in the constants = $\pm 0.02 \sim 0.04$.

solution using a Elico LI-10 T pH-meter at 30°. Representative pH-titration plots in case of Ni(histidine)(glycine) system are presented in Fig. 1. The formation constants were calculated by the literature methods⁴. The results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The $\log K_{Ni.L}^{Ni}$ values are in the order, glycine $\approx$ α -alanine $<$ aspartic acid for the amino acids, and glycollic $\approx$ lactic $<$ malic acid for the corresponding hydroxy acids⁵. The $K_{Ni.A.L}^{Ni.A}$ values are higher than $K_{Ni.L}^{Ni}$ for A=2,2'-bipyridyl, and significantly lower for A=histidine.

The higher values of $K_{Ni.(bipy).L}^{Ni.(bipy.)}$ than $K_{Ni.(hist.).L}^{Ni.(hist.)}$ arise due to electrostatic repulsion between the primary ligand histidine and secondary ligands. Histidine is anionic while 2,2'-bipyridyl is neutral in the NiAL complexes.

The higher stability of the Ni^{II} complexes with amino acid than the corresponding complexes with hydroxy acid complexes arise from the greater tendency of Ni^{II} to bind with a nitrogen ligand as compared to oxygen.

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Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with Benzoic Acid Hydrazones

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IN view of the current interest in the biological activity¹ and structures of hydrazides and hydrazones, a systematic study of *p*-hydroxy- and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzaldehyde benzoic acid hydrazone (abbreviated as HBBH and HMBBH, respectively) have been undertaken. Their complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been isolated and characterised by physicochemical methods.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Commercial ethanol was used after purification by distillation.

p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde benzoic acid hydrazone (HBBH): Ethanolic solutions of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.05 mol, 6.10 g) and benzoic acid hydrazide (0.05 mol, 6.80 g) were refluxed for 3 h. The resulting white powdery solid separated on cooling the mixture to room temperature, was filtered, washed with ethanol, petroleum ether and finally dried over calcium chloride under reduced pressure, HBBH (80%), m.p. 215°, was soluble in hot ethanol.

4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde benzoic acid hydrazone (HMBBH): It was obtained from 3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.05 mol, 7.60 g)